

Studies in the Stobbe Condensation : Migration of the Double Bond*

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Manuscript received 30 January 1976, accepted 26 September 1977.

The Stobbe condensation of desoxybenzoin with dimethyl succinate, and of α -tetralone and cyclohexanone with diethyl homophthalate yield the corresponding alkylidene esteracids, 3-methoxycarbonyl-4,5-diphenylpent-3-enoic acid, ethyl 2-*o*-carboxyphenyl-2, 2- Δ' -tetralonylacetae and methyl 2-*o*-carboxyphenylcyclohexylidene acetate under mild reaction conditions. These α , β -unsaturated esters under more drastic experimental conditions lead to 3-methoxycarbonyl-4,5-diphenylpent-4-enoic acid, ethyl 2-*o*-carboxyphenyl-2-(3',4'-dihydro)- α -naphthylacetate and methyl 2-*o*-carboxyphenyl-2-cyclohexenyl acetate by migration of the double bond forming the alkenyl systems.

THE Stobbe condensation¹ of ketones with succinic esters could yield alkylidene (2) or alkenyl products (3), if the ketone has a methylene group adjacent to it, and often a mixture is formed.

The condensation of desoxybenzoin (1 : $R_1 = R_2 = Ph$) with dimethyl succinate have been carried out by several workers^{2,3,4} in presence of sodium ethoxide in ether, dry sodium ethoxide, and sodium hydride in benzene. They^{2,3,4} reported the formation of a diacid (3 : $R_1 = R_2 = Ph$; $R = H$) m.p. 150-51, the structure was based probably on the phenyl groups favouring a double bond in conjugation with them². Effecting the Stobbe condensation in presence of butanolic potassium tert. butoxide under mild conditions of temperature (20 to 30°) and for a short period (30 to 50 min.) gave 3-methoxycarbonyl-4, 5-diphenylpent-3-enoic acid (2 : $R_1 = R_2 = Ph$, $R = Me$) m.p. 119°. When the condensation was conducted in refluxing tert. butoxide for 2.5 hr. it gave 3-methoxycarbonyl-4, 5-diphenylpent-4-enoic acid (3 : $R_1 = R_2 = Ph$, $R = Me$) m.p. 80°. Saponification of these acid esters yielded the corresponding diacids, m.p. 170° (2 : $R_1 = R_2 = Ph$, $R = H$) and m.p. 95° (3 : $R = R = Ph$, $R = H$) respectively. Structures could be definitely assigned to these compounds on the basis of their (i) equivalent weights and analytical data (ii) oxidation of ester-acid and diacid (3) with alkaline permanganate gave benzaldehyde facily and instantaneously while the acid-ester and diacid (2) did not yield benzaldehyde on oxidation (iii) ir. spectrum of the carbonyl region of 2 : $R = Me$ showed a single overlapped peak at 1710 cm^{-1} for an α, β -unsaturated ester and acid carboxyl (lit. 1730-1717 cm^{-1} and 1725-1700 $cm^{-1,6,7}$ whereas 3 : $R = Me$ shows two peaks at 1710 cm^{-1} (saturated acid 1725-1700 cm^{-1}) and 1735 cm^{-1} (saturated ester 1750-1735 cm^{-1})^{6,7}.

Thus under mild conditions, the double bond is formed as would be expected from the condensation of the methylene of the succinic ester (viz.2) whereas under refluxing conditions, the double bond is in the migrated position as in (3). This migration of the double bond was further conclusively shown by refluxing the ester-acid (2 : $R = Me$) with butanolic potassium tert. butoxide when it was converted into ester-acid (3 : $R = Me$).

When the reaction was done under the reaction conditions of earlier workers² and the crude half-ester saponified *in situ*, it was observed that a diacid, m.p. 150-51° was obtained with the expected equivalent weight of 148, as reported. By crystallisation from benzene however, it could be easily separated into two different diacids (2 : $R = H$), m.p. 170° and (3 : $R = H$) m.p. 94°.

Lowenthal and Pappo⁸ have reported the closely allied condensation of a Stobbe pattern in the reaction of diethyl homophthalate. For alternative double bond formation studies the tert. butoxide catalysed condensation of diethyl homophthalate and α -tetralone was investigated. In this reaction Chatterjea et al.⁹ have found that the ethylenic double bond is situated in the alicyclic ring in conjugation with the aromatic ring (as in 7). When the reaction was conducted under the mild conditions as above ethyl-2-*o*-carboxyphenyl-2,- Δ' -tetralonylacetae (6 : $R = Et$) m.p. 163° was formed. Under the more drastic conditions of the reaction however, ethyl 2-*o*-carboxyphenyl-2-(3',4'-dihydro)- α -naphthyl acetate (7 : $R = Et$), m.p. 145° was formed. As in the earlier case the structural assignment could be made on the spectral and chemical data (see experimental). The migration was also effected by refluxion of the acid (6 : $R = Et$) with alkoxide when 7 : $R = Et$ was obtained.

In the condensation of cyclohexanone and diethyl homophthalate, the viscous half-ester

* Presented at the Annual Session of the Indian Science Congress, Nagpur, January, 1974.

obtained under the milder conditions largely solidified to yield ethyl 2-*o*-carboxyphenylcyclohexylidene acetate (8: R=Et), m.p. 111°. This on refluxing with potassium tert. butoxide gave an uncrystallisable oily mixture of half-esters⁸ from which the diacids could be obtained as reported by Lowenthal and Pappo⁹. Thus, in this case, though the alkylidene system is the major product, the alkenyl system cannot be obtained easily for the initial system is also the thermodynamically stabler one.

The experiments indicate that the primary product in the Stobbe reaction is the alkylidene system, the alkenyl compound getting formed in a secondary double bond migration step which occurs only under more drastic conditions of refluxing alkoxide, Refluxing hydroxide does not result in migration but only in saponification.

Experimental

Stobbe Condensation with Desoxybenzoin :

A. Desoxybenzoin (19.6 g) and dimethyl succinate (16 g) were added to butanolic potassium tert. butoxide (from 4 g. potassium and 120 ml. butanol) and stirred magnetically under inert anhydrous conditions for 40 min. Then the reaction mixture was poured in ice-cold 3N-hydrochloric acid. The separated solid was filtered and taken up in benzene. The filtrate was extracted in benzene. The combined organic layers were repeatedly extracted with sodium carbonate solution. The alkaline solution on acidification gave 3-methoxycarbonyl-4, 5-diphenylpent-3-enoic acid

(2: R₁=R₂=Ph, R=Me) (5.7 g), crystallized from ether-petroleum ether, m.p. 119°; found: eq.wt. 309; C, 73.2; H, 5.6. reqd. for C₁₉H₁₈O₄, eq.wt. 310; C, 73.5; H, 5.8%; uv: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 235 nm., log ε 4.11; ir: 1710 cm⁻¹ (α,β-unsaturated ester and acid carboxyl). When treated with alkaline potassium permanganate, the permanganate got slowly decolourised but no benzaldehyde was formed.

Desoxybenzoin (9.8 g) and dimethyl succinate (7.3 g) were added to butanolic potassium tert.

butoxide (from 2 g. potassium and 60 ml. butanol) and refluxed for 2.5 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured in ice-cold 3N-hydrochloric acid, and the product worked up as before. The alkaline layer on acidification gave 3-methoxycarbonyl-4,5-diphenylpent-4-enoic acid (3: R₁=R₂=Ph, R=Me) (7 g), crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 80°; found: eq. wt. 309; C, 73.2; H, 5.9; reqd. for C₁₉H₁₈O₄, eq.wt. 310; C, 73.5; H, 5.87%; uv: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 223, 253 nm, log 4.06; ir: 1710 and 1735 cm⁻¹ (acid and ester). On treatment with alkaline potassium permanganate it gave a strong smell of benzaldehyde. After partial oxidation the material was extracted with ether and the solvent was removed, addition of alcoholic solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine and sulphuric acid yielded the 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, mixed m.p. 235°.

The acid-ester (1 g) was refluxed with 8% aq. sodium hydroxide (25 ml) for 6 hr. On acidification, it gave 3-carboxy-4, 5-diphenylpent-4-enoic acid (3: R₁=R₂=Ph, R=H) (0.9 g), crystallized from rectified spirit, m.p. 94°; found: eq.wt. 149; C, 72.6; H, 5.6; reqd. for C₁₈H₁₆O₄, eq.wt. 148; C, 72.9; H, 5.4%; uv: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 226, 257 nm, log 4.13, 4.06. With alkaline potassium permanganate it gave a smell of benzaldehyde, which was identified through its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone as above.

Isomerization of 3-methoxycarbonyl-4,5-diphenylpent-3-enoic acid with refluxing potassium tert. butoxide. 3-Methoxy carbonyl-4,5-diphenylpent-3-enoic acid (0.5 g) was mixed with butanolic potassium tert. butoxide (from 0.5 g potassium and 15 ml tert. butanol) and refluxed for 2.5 hr. The reaction mixture on working up as above gave 3-methoxycarbonyl-4,5-diphenylpent-4-enoic acid (0.4 g), crystallized from ether-petroleum ether, m.p. and m.m.p, 80°.

Stobbe Condensation of α-tetralone and diethyl homophthalate :

α-Tetralone (3.7 g) and diethyl homophthalate (5 g) were added to butanolic potassium tert. butoxide (from 1 g. potassium and 30 ml. butanol) and stirred magnetically under inert anhydrous conditions for 50 min. The reaction was worked up as usual when ethyl 2-*o*-carboxyphenyl-2,2-Δ¹-tetralonyl acetate (6: R=E) (5.9 g) was obtained. It was crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 163°, found: eq. wt. 333; C, 74.8; H, 6.1, reqd. for C₂₁H₂₀O₄, eq. wt. 336; C, 75; H, 5.95% uv: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 244, 275 nm, log ε 3.89, 4.03 g; ir 1670 and 1715 cm⁻¹ (aryl carboxyl and α,β-unsaturated ester).

Saponification gave the diacid (6: R=H) m.p. 204°; eq. wt. found: 151; reqd; 153; uv: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 252-256 nm, log ε 4.04; ir: 1670 cm⁻¹ (aryl carboxyl and α,β-unsaturated acid).

Stobbe condensation with cyclohexanone : A mixture of cyclohexanone (2.5 g.), diethyl homophthalate

(5.9 g.) and potassium tert. butoxide (from 1 g. potassium and 30 ml. butanol) was stirred at 30° for 45 min. The reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold 3N-hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether, and the ethereal solution extracted with ice-cold sodium carbonate solution. The alkaline phase was acidified and the oily material got, on trituration with benzene-petroleum ether gave methyl 2-*o*-carboxyphenyl-cyclohexylidene acetate (8 : R = Et) (7 g.), m.p. 109°, crystallized from ether-petroleum ether m.p. 112°; eq.wt. found : 286 ; reqd. for C₁₇H₂₀O₄, 288.

Saponification of the ester-acid (1 g) gave the cyclohexylidene diacid (8 : R = H), m.p. 188° (rectified spirit) lit⁸ 183-4° eq.wt. found : 131 ; reqd. 130.

Isomerisation of the acid-ester (4 g.) with refluxing tert. butoxide (from 0.5 g potassium and 15 ml butanol), on working up in the usual way yielded an oil (3.8 g) which did not crystallise. This oil on saponification gave a diacid (3.0 g) which on crystallisation from acetic acid gave the diacid, m.p. and m.m.p. 188° (1.8 g) and the filtrate yielded the diacid, m.p, 140-2° (0.5 g) lit⁹. 141-5°.

Acknowledgements

For financial assistance we are grateful to the U.G.C. (V.R.P.) and to the CSIR (BHP). We thank Dr. M.M. Wadia of University of Pune ; Dr. S.M. Verma of B.H.U., and the C.D.R.I. Lucknow and R.R.L. Hyderabad for the analysis and spectra.

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